

DIAGNOSTICS OF THE FORMATION OF HISTORICAL THINKING IN THE HISTORY TEACHER THROUGH HISTORICAL WORKS OF ART

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Abstract: In this article, the author reveals the structure of the formation of historical thinking in the future history teacher based on a comprehensive approach to the study of historical sciences. The problem of formation of historical thinking is considered in the theory and practice of training future history teacher. The essence, tasks, characteristics of the teacher's historical thinking in the study of historical subjects. Historical thinking is formed thanks to methodological techniques, special organizational forms of teaching, game models and other active methods of teaching history.

Key words: future history teacher, humanization of pedagogical education, teaching methods, historical thinking, formation of historical thinking, history teaching methodology, game modeling

Let us now consider how the state of development of pedagogical sciences correlates with the practice of teaching history, with the professional training of teachers and the level of development of historical thinking among future history teachers

At this stage of the study, the following methods were used: analysis of documentation (plans, thematic planning, classroom journals, student notes, student survey materials); attending lectures (30) and seminars (30); interviews with teachers; observation; questioning of teachers (Appendix 2, table 2.1).

When studying pedagogical experience, we tried to determine what place the study of historical fiction occupies in the process of teaching history by a future teacher of history; to identify the degree of purposefulness, consistency in the activities of teachers in the formation of historical thinking in the future history teachers; fix the most common forms and methods of working with them.

Analysis of the results of the study showed that teachers are aware of the need to work with historical fiction. In the questionnaires, they note that the study of historical fiction forms the basis of scientific historical thinking in future history teachers (82%); instills interest in history (81%); contributes to the formation of skills in future history teachers, to independently obtain knowledge from various historical fiction (58%); develops student-teacher collaboration (47).

When assessing the educational potential of teacher sources, first of all, their educational function is singled out. Further, they note their significance as a carrier of information. And only in third place is the developing function of working with literary texts. Teachers do not fully realize that the formation of students' skills to independently work with historical fiction as sources is the starting point for solving the problems of teaching and education.

According to the questionnaires, 34% of the respondents-teachers use sources almost every class and 35% - periodically. As a rule, historical literary works are included in the lecture presentation of the teacher himself. Independent work of future history teachers with

historical literary works is less common. Practice shows that in order to organize independent work of future history teachers with historical literary works, teachers use various types of classes.

When attending classes of teachers and interviewing them, we found that the methods of working with historical literary works, most often, are aimed at extracting information from historical literary works and analyzing it under the guidance of a teacher.

With a few exceptions, we have not seen in the process of teaching the use by the teacher of special methods of work on the formation of students' knowledge about rational ways of studying historical literary works and developing the relevant skills. We found an example of such activity in the teacher Abdullajonov Nigora organized the work of students with historical literary works on the basis of the memo "How to study a historical literary work."

But even when working with a historical literary text on the basis of a memo, students, as a rule, independently carried out only actions related to identifying the attributive features of the source, identifying unfamiliar events and terms. The teacher himself asked questions that required students to analyze the content of the text and draw conclusions about what they had read. With this teaching method, students mastered the content of this historical literary text, but they did not develop the ability to independently study new historical literary works, since they did not know how to plan their actions to carry out a number of mental operations necessary to work with a historical literary work.

In thematic planning, we rarely found attempts to outline the stages and tasks of lectures and seminars to develop any skills, including historical thinking.

Elements of the purposeful process of forming the skills of historical thinking in working with historical works of art among students, we observed only in the practice of individual teachers with a high level of professional culture. We have studied and summarized the experience of leading history teachers listed above

The experience of Abdullaev Muzrobon Nulomovich (NamSU) is interesting from the point of view of the formation of students' historical thinking skills in the analysis of billitertics and fiction. For example, the teacher offered the following tasks: to prepare a reflection-story "My favorite book about the war." This aimed students at working with several historical pieces of art.

In the practice of their teaching, the work of students with historical works of art is carried out systematically. At the same time, teachers use sources of alternative content in the classroom.

The experience of advanced teachers testified to the fact that teachers have a focus on the use of historical literary works of different content in teaching, the introduction of texts of artistic historical content into the learning process, the problematic nature of the study of historical literary works, and the creative use of various forms of independent work of students.

At the same time, systematic work with historical artistic literary works manifested itself mainly only in the fact that students regularly turned to historical sources. There were no attempts by teachers to create their own system of purposeful stage-by-stage processing of individual actions, which would ensure the mastery of the ability to independently select, study and analyze literary texts about the past.

A generalization of the mass practice of history teachers in using historical literary works in order to form historical thinking in future teachers allowed us to draw the following conclusions:

- 1) teachers, in general, are oriented towards working with historical literary works, they are aware of the importance of using them for university historical education;
- 2) most of them use historical literary works in the educational process, but mainly for informational purposes;
- 3) teachers experience difficulties in determining the structure of educational information skills, in planning and organizing purposeful, phased work on the development of historical thinking and independently work with historical literary works, compare and carry out criticism of various literary texts.

Let us now consider how the revealed state of readiness of teachers to work with historical literary works is reflected in the results of teaching future teachers of history. We were primarily interested in the following:

- 1) the attitude of students to the study of historical artistic literary works;
- 2) the level of formation of historical thinking;
- 3) the ability of future history teachers to analyze historical literary works.

Teachers in their questionnaires note the pragmatic attitude of students to work with historical literary works. Teachers believe that future history teachers work with historical literary works because it will be useful to them when they enter the magistracy (73%). 24% of teachers note that their students are interested in this type of cognitive activity. The rest believe that future teachers of history are often frightened off by the complexity of independent search and analysis of historical literary works.

The assessments given by teachers almost coincide with the opinion of students (217 students from 3 universities were surveyed - see the questionnaire in Appendix 2.2). According to the questionnaires of teachers, 52% of students are not interested in acquiring knowledge based on work with historical literary works. This is also evidenced by 51% of the answers of the students themselves, who prefer to listen to teachers.

We studied the attitude of students to historical artistic literary works. When answering the question: "What historical literary works should be used when studying the past?" students put the textbook in the first place - 40%. The text of lectures and preparation for seminars were named the most important source by 36% of the respondents, and only 4% of respondents showed historical literary works. From this it follows that teachers poorly form a value attitude towards the foundations of scientific knowledge of the past in the future teacher of history on the basis of historical literary works.

Future teachers involved in the ascertaining experiment, in the course of researching the ability to independently study historical literary works, were asked to answer the question: "What historical literary works do you need to improve historical knowledge and will you begin to analyze a historical literary work? » Some future history teachers (8%) answered that it is necessary to know who the author of this source is and at what time it was written.

Then future teachers of history were given a fragment of the novel by E. Marshall "The Winner". - M.: Enlightenment. -1995. - (about Alexander the Great. About his campaign in Asia with an army consisting of Macedonians, Illyrians, Thracians and contingents of Greek states - a common numbering 30,000-40,000 people.) It was proposed to read a fragment of the novel and complete the following tasks in writing: 1). State the main ideas of the novel. 2). Put questions to the proposed text. 3). Give answers to the most important of them using the text of the novel. 4). Draw possible conclusions from the fragment of the novel.

The results of the survey were as follows. The main ideas of the fragment of the novel were able to highlight only a small part of the students surveyed - 17%.

Questions to the text of the novel could be asked by the majority of future history teachers (78%), but they were mainly of a reproductive nature, for example: The events of what era are reflected in the novel? What conquests of A. Macdonsky are described in the novel? Questions focused on the analysis and explanation of the information presented in the novel were less common.

All future history teachers could find answers to their questions. Conclusions from the text were made by 44% of the students, but almost all of them were direct (obvious). The rest of the future teachers of history only tried, but could not formulate their thoughts in such a way that they reflected the essence and meaning of the content of the novel.

To identify the level of formation of historical thinking, future history teachers were given the task of comparing the educational material when studying the issue of the military campaigns of Alexander the Great with the description of the military campaigns of Alexander the Great in E. Marshall's novel "The Winner". Students were required to do the following:

- compare educational material and excerpts from E. Marshall's novel "The Winner" with a description of the military campaigns of Alexander the Great and identify similarities and differences in the campaigns of A. Macedonian ;
- after analyzing two sources, determine whether the described military campaigns of Alexander the Great in the novel are reliable documentary historical facts or are they all authorial, fictitious?

The written control cut showed the following results. In general, the students preferred the description of the military campaigns of Alexander the Great to the educational material presented in the educational material. But only 12% made attempts to substantiate their position. Most of the students found it difficult to justify their decision. Solving the tasks set for future teachers of history. The answers were intuitive.

The results obtained in the course of the ascertaining experiment testified that the majority of future history teachers possessed historical thinking at the reproductive level. They can extract the necessary information from the literary text and retell it. They know about some actions to determine the attributes of educational material. But at the same time, future teachers of history are weakly oriented toward an independent understanding of a historical work of art, to performing operations on the analysis, generalization and independent assessment of its content.

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